

The Registration of Trademarks in Europe

Malta and Luxembourg lead the ranking of countries by value of trademark registrations

Eurostat calculates the amount of the number of registered trademark applications on the value of the gross domestic product. Brands are an important indicator of innovation, especially for the service sector. The Community trademark confers on its owner a uniform law applicable in all Member States of the European Union through a single procedure that simplifies trademark policies at European level.

Ranking of European countries by value of trademark registrations in 2021. Luxembourg and Malta are in first place by value of the number of trademarks registered with an amount equal to 202.17, followed by both Estonia with a value equal to 196.91 and Austria with an amount equal to 142.72. In the middle of the table there are Belgium with an amount equal to 106.00 units, followed by Poland with an amount equal to 93.14 and by Greece with an amount equal to 92.25. North Macedonia closes the ranking with a value of 20.11, followed by Montenegro with an amount of 19.17 and Ukraine with an amount of 13.65. On average in 2021 the value of the amount of registered trademarks was equal to an amount of 95.85 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change in trademark registrations between 2014 and 2021. Bosnia and Croatia are in first place by value of the percentage change in trademarks registered between 2014 and 2021 with an amount equal to a value of 82% equal to a value of 29 units. Turkey is in second place with a percentage change equal to an amount of 55% equal to an absolute value of 7 and Estonia is in third place with an amount equal to 50% equal to 65 units. In the middle of the table are Italy with a percentage change equal to 22% equal to an amount of 21 units, followed by Finland with a percentage change equal to 21% equal to 22 units and Sweden with a percentage change equal to 15% equal to an amount of 17 units. Cyprus and Iceland close the ranking with a percentage change of -47% equal to -64 units. On average, the value of trademark registration grew by an amount equal to 19% between 2014 and 2021.

Clusterization. A clustering is carried out below with the use of the k-Means algorithm. The k-Means algorithm is a supervised algorithm and therefore it is necessary to indicate in advance the optimal number of clusters. To overcome this problem, the Silhouette coefficient can be used. The Silhouette coefficient varies between -1 and +1. To make an optimal choice, you need to select the value of the Silhouette coefficient close to 1. By applying the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient, the following clusters have been selected:

- Cluster 1: France, Czech Republic, Poland, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Ireland, Slovakia;
- Cluster 2: Malta, Luxembourg;
- Cluster 3: Netherlands, Germany, Slovenia, Bulgaria, Spain, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, Belgium, Denmark, United Kingdom;
- Cluster 4: Turkey, North Macedonia, Ukraine, Serbia, Montenegro;
- Cluster 5: Switzerland, Estonia, Austria;
- Cluster 6: Iceland, Cyprus;
- Cluster 7: Israel, Croatia, Bosnia, Romania, Norway, Hungary.

It is possible to rank clusters based on the value of the median of the constituent elements of the cluster. The following ordering of the clusters is therefore determined below, namely: C2 with a median value of 202.17, followed by C5 with a median value of 159.51 units, followed by C3 with a

value of 117.42 units, followed by C1 with a value of 87.85 units, followed by C6 with a value of 72.30 units, followed by C7 with a value of 63.08 units, followed by C4 with a value of 20 , 25. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives, i.e. C2> C5> C3> C1> C6> C7> C4.

Prediction. A comparison was then made between 7 different algorithms to predict the value of the trademark application in Europe. The algorithms were organized based on their ability to minimize MSE, RMSE and MAE statistical errors and to optimize the R-square. Based on the analysis, the following ranking of the algorithms results, namely:

- Gradient Boosting with a value of 5;
- AdaBoost with a value of 6;
- Linear Regression with a value of 13;
- Tree with a value of 15;
- Random Forest with a value of 20;
- Knn with a value of 24;
- Neural Network with a value of 28.

In particular, by applying the best performing algorithm or the Gradient Boosting it is possible to calculate a downward prediction for the registration of trademarks in Europe with a predicted value equal to -0.157852632 in absolute value and equal to -0.164410373 in percentage value.

Conclusions. In summary, it is possible to verify that the value of the trademark applications in Europe has grown from an amount of 85.9 units up to a value of 95.8 units between 2014 and 2021 or an absolute change equal to an amount of 10 units. and a percentage change equal to a value of 12.00%. However, as indicated by the cluster analysis, there is a great heterogeneity in Europe in the ability of countries to attract trademark registrations. In particular, there are some countries which evidently show a competitive advantage which is very likely also of a speculative type as in the case of Malta and Luxembourg. In fact, in these countries it is possible to easily carry out trademark registrations in order to also enjoy the related tax advantages. Finally, the analysis using machine learning algorithms shows the presence of a tendency to decline for trademark applications in Europe. From the point of view of economic policies, it is necessary to emphasize that the growth of trademark registrations is an essential element of the intangible economy that supports the knowledge economy.

Reference:

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	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2	Totale
Gradient Boosting	1	1	2	1	5
AdaBoost	2	2	1	1	6
Linear Regression	3	3	4	3	13
Tree	4	4	3	4	15
Random Forest	5	5	5	5	20
kNN	6	6	6	6	24
Neural Network	7	7	7	7	28

Clusterizzazione con algoritmo k-Means. C2>C5>C3>C1>C6>C7>C4.

